

Integrating Building Openings into BIM Workflow Management for Optimal MEP Detailed Design: A Study in Building Construction

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Abstract

This thesis explores the integration of building openings within the Building Information Modelling (BIM) framework for MEP detailed design in the industrial plant construction context. It encompasses a thorough literature review, providing an overview of BIM in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry, underlining the significance of MEP design, and investigating coordination methodologies. The study also features a comprehensive case study with the primary aim of developing an optimized workflow for better managing cutouts intended for MEP equipment. The case study focuses on improving the management of cutouts within an ongoing industrial plant construction project. The investigation assesses the use of automation tools and techniques to seamlessly integrate these openings into the BIM workflow. The outcomes highlight several advantages, including enhanced coordination, reduced rework, increased efficiency in MEP design, and the potential for automation. Furthermore, the study explores the improvement of coordination both within and among external departments. The thesis concludes by summarizing

its contributions to the field and presenting recommendations for future research directions. By addressing a notable gap in the literature related to the integration of building openings into the BIM workflow for MEP detailed design in the industrial plant construction sector, this work makes a substantial contribution to advancing the state of BIM and MEP detailed design.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/LjAXT0dB6ts>

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